

iTempDT: AI-Powered Digital Twin for Forecasting Indoor Temperature in Smart Buildings

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Abstract—This work presents iTempDT, an AI-driven Digital Twin (DT) approach that uses deep learning to forecast indoor temperature based on Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) system operations. Accurate temperature forecasting is essential for smart buildings (SBs), which aim to optimize energy efficiency without compromising occupant comfort. iTempDT addresses this need by providing accurate and timely forecasts that allow intelligent HVAC control and energy-efficient decision-making. At the core of iTempDT is a Temporal Convolutional Network (TCN) integrated with an attention mechanism to capture temporal dynamics and feature dependencies from multivariate time series data collected from both indoor and outdoor sensors. The model is trained for multi-step indoor temperature forecasting, explicitly conditioned on the recent HVAC status (ON/OFF), allowing for real-time predictions as well as scenario-based simulations. Also, an interactive dashboard enables real-time visualization and virtual control of HVAC settings. To promote sustainable and energy-conscious AI practices, iTempDT integrates a Green AI approach by applying post-training quantization. This reduces the model size and speeds up inference, making it suitable for deployment on low-power edge devices. The DT prototype was developed at the ICAR-CNR IoT Lab in Rende, Italy. iTempDT shows strong performance across key metrics (MAE, R^2 , and RPD). Finally, the proposed approach is compared with other state-of-the-art models.

Index Terms—AI-Driven Digital Twin, IoT, Smart Buildings, HVAC Control, Deep Learning, TCN-Attention.

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of Digital Twins (DT) [1] has emerged as a powerful paradigm in the context of Smart Buildings (SBs), of-

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fering real-time virtual replicas of physical systems to optimize operations, maintenance, and performance. One of the critical applications of DTs in SBs lies in managing indoor climate through Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems [2]. HVAC systems account for a substantial portion of the energy consumption in SBs, and their intelligent control is essential to maintain thermal comfort while minimizing energy use [2].

Accurate indoor temperature forecasting plays a vital role in enabling smarter and more efficient HVAC control. Traditional rule-based or Proportional–Integral–Derivative controller (PID)-based systems lack adaptability and responsiveness to dynamic environmental changes [3]. Recent advances in artificial intelligence (AI) models provide an opportunity to model complex, nonlinear interactions between environmental factors, occupancy, and HVAC operations. In the existing literature, numerous studies have explored Machine Learning (ML) [4]–[11] and Deep Learning (DL) [12]–[21] techniques to forecast indoor temperature in SBs for energy efficiency. However, few of these approaches are embedded within a comprehensive DT framework. Existing DT-based studies in SBs often focus on specific objectives such as security [22], anomaly detection [23], or heritage conservation [24], [25]. These works often lack the integration of DL-based forecasting models that explicitly consider HVAC system status (ON/OFF) as part of the predictive process. Thus, a comprehensive DT approach that combines real-time sensor data, HVAC behavior modeling, and DL forecasting remains underexplored in the literature.

Among DL models, Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCNs) with attention have shown strong performance in time series forecasting by capturing both short- and long-range dependencies, enabling parallel computation, and ensuring gradient stability [26]. However, this architecture has not been explored in SB with DT frameworks for HVAC-aware (ON/OFF) indoor temperature forecasting. To address this gap, we propose iTempDT, a DT-based approach that integrates TCNs with a custom attention mechanism to model multivariate sensor data and forecast multistep indoor temperature under different HVAC operating modes. In addition, the iTempDT approach architecture is also designed to be lightweight and quantization-friendly [27], making it suitable for use on edge devices such as Raspberry Pi or low-power IoT controllers within SBs. This design choice aligns with the

emerging paradigm of Green AI, which promotes the development of ML models that not only deliver high predictive performance but also minimize computational and environmental costs. In contrast to general AI models that prioritize accuracy alone, Green AI emphasizes sustainable and efficient use of computational resources. This is particularly important for SB applications deployed on energy-constrained edge devices, where resource efficiency is critical. A widely used Green AI technique is quantization [27], [28], which reduces numerical precision (e.g., from 32-bit to 16-bit), leading to smaller models, faster inference, and lower power consumption with minimal accuracy loss. In summary, the main contributions of this paper are as follows.

- Developing the iTempDT approach, which combines a TCN with an attention mechanism to forecast indoor temperature using multivariate sensor data, including a desired HVAC status.
- Presenting an interactive dashboard that visualizes both historical and forecasted indoor temperatures, enabling virtual HVAC control for real-time decision support.
- Developing a lightweight, quantization-friendly model suitable for deployment on edge devices such as Raspberry Pi and low-power IoT controllers in SBs.
- Demonstrating superior performance of the model used compared to baseline DL models (i.e., ANN, RNN, CNN, LSTM) across key evaluation metrics, including *MAE*, R^2 , and *RPD*.

The model used in iTempDT adopts a combined TCN and attention architecture to improve forecasting accuracy, while also integrates Green AI principles through quantization. This makes iTempDT both accurate and energy-efficient, enabling real-time, edge-based deployment and supporting scalable, sustainable AI in smart environments.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews related work on SBs and indoor temperature forecasting, and also discusses the role of DT in SB applications. Section III explains the proposed iTempDT approach, while Section IV presents some results and discusses them. The final section concludes the paper and outlines future directions.

II. RELATED WORK

This section reviews recent studies on indoor temperature prediction in SBs, as well as various DT approaches applied in different scenarios, such as energy-efficient HVAC control, security, etc.

A. Indoor Temperature Prediction through ML and DL

In the context of SBs, data-driven models have become pivotal for predicting indoor temperature, enabling more efficient HVAC control and energy management. Over the years, a wide range of AI techniques—including traditional statistical approaches, ML, and DL models—have been employed for this task [29], [30].

Initially, classical statistical models such as ARIMA were commonly used in the early 2000s for predicting indoor temperature trends [4]. However, with the increasing availability

of sensor data and computational resources, ML algorithms have gained prominence. Techniques such as Support Vector Regression (SVR) [5], Random Forests (RF) [6], and XGBoost [7] have shown strong predictive capabilities in various studies. For instance, works like [8]–[10] highlight the effectiveness of ensemble-based models (e.g., RF, Extra Trees) in modeling temporal dynamics and HVAC-related behaviors. In recent years, the use of artificial neural networks (ANNs) and more advanced DL architectures has become increasingly prevalent, given their ability to capture complex, nonlinear relationships among features in SB environments [11], [12]. Several studies have confirmed that ANN-based models can achieve reliable performance in forecasting indoor temperature [13]–[17].

Moreover, Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks have been shown [19] to provide more accurate short-term indoor temperature predictions (5 and 30 minutes ahead) compared to traditional models such as SVM, decision trees, and backpropagation-based neural networks. Similarly, Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs)—a streamlined alternative to LSTMs—have also been applied effectively. In [20], a hierarchical attention-GRU architecture was proposed for indoor temperature forecasting, outperforming several baseline ML and DL models. Besides, [21] introduced an LSTM-based sequence-to-sequence framework that successfully predicted temperatures across multiple indoor zones. Enhancements such as error correction modules, as seen in [19], further improved the accuracy of LSTM models for short-term predictions. Additionally, ensemble learning strategies have shown promise in combining the strengths of various ML and DL models. The DEML framework [18] combined ML and DL ensembles for indoor temperature forecasting in Australian urban settings, outperforming standalone models like RF, SVM, gradient boosting, and LSTM.

B. Digital Twins in Smart Buildings

Numerous DT approaches have been used in SBs so far, as described below.

In our previous work [2], we proposed a DT approach for indoor temperature forecasting in SBs. This approach utilized LSTM and BiLSTM models for single-step-ahead prediction, evaluated using k-fold cross-validation to ensure robust performance. A cloud-based DT framework [23] has been used to help protect historic buildings by combining IoT sensors, semantic data modeling, and cloud platforms. In one example, the City Theater in Norrköping was digitally modeled to track indoor conditions such as temperature, humidity, and CO₂ in real time. This made it possible to spot harmful changes, such as sudden humidity spikes, and take early action to protect materials such as wood and plaster [23]. On a similar idea, a related study [24] focused more on energy efficiency in historic buildings. By linking IoT data with AI and ML in the cloud, the system predicted energy use, detected faults, and controlled HVAC systems automatically. Tests in three historic buildings showed better comfort, lower energy use, and fewer climate-related risks, such as dampness in the basement [24]. Though

they didn't specify the AI-based model's names. Together, these last two approaches show how DT, combined with cloud and AI technologies, can support both conservation and smart energy management in heritage buildings.

DT technologies are increasingly being used to enhance HVAC performance, energy efficiency, and real-time monitoring in smart buildings. One notable approach, HVACDT, integrates Building Information Modeling (BIM) with real-time IoT sensor data to optimize HVAC control [31]. Using an ANN to model thermal behavior and a Multi-Objective Genetic Algorithm (MOGA) for optimizing temperature setpoints and airflow, the system achieved over 13% energy savings during peak summer without compromising comfort. Similarly, a DT system was proposed for the continuous monitoring of HVAC assets during the operation and maintenance phase [32]. By linking real-time sensor data with extended IFC models, and applying a Bayesian change-point detection algorithm, the system accurately detected anomalies in HVAC components like pumps, enabling timely maintenance and reducing energy waste.

Focusing on heritage sites, another study introduced a DT system for regulating relative humidity in underground spaces [25]. By combining real-time humidity data with airflow simulation, the system dynamically controlled ventilation to preserve wall surfaces, preventing mold and condensation while reducing energy use. The framework, built on HBIM, shows how DTs can support both conservation and smart environmental control.

Beyond HVAC, DT also plays a role in indoor positioning and security. A Wi-Fi-based localization system used edge computing and Bayesian inference to estimate user locations in real time, achieving meter-level accuracy with minimal infrastructure [33]. This method enhances occupancy detection and enables smarter HVAC and anomaly response in SBs.

In the context of home security, another edge-based system processed sensor data locally using kNN and DNN to detect intrusions with low latency and strong privacy [22]. Through online learning, the system adapts to individual behavior patterns, reducing false alarms and ensuring fast, private decision-making without cloud dependence.

Finally, a GRU-based DT framework was proposed for managing massive IoT data in SBs [34]. Virtual agents powered by GRU neural networks learned temporal patterns to make real-time decisions on data storage and processing. A blockchain layer authenticated high-priority data, while edge computing handled the rest, improving security, reducing latency, and outperforming previous LSTM-based methods.

Together, these studies highlight the diverse applications of DT in smart and heritage building from HVAC control and anomaly detection to localization, intrusion prevention, and efficient data handling—showcasing the combined power of AI, edge computing, and BIM-based modeling.

To the best of our knowledge, the literature misses comprehensive approaches based on DT and DL for indoor temperature forecasting that are designed for making predictions according to chosen HVAC ON/OFF conditions. To address

this gap, this work proposes and validates iTempDT, a Digital Twin-based approach that uses DL models and sensor data to effectively forecast indoor temperature under varying HVAC conditions.

III. THE PROPOSED DT APPROACH AND ITS IMPLEMENTATION

This section outlines the iTempDT approach, data preprocessing steps, AI model integration, and key design parts. Due to space constraints, this section presents both the details of the proposed approach and its instantiation in a real-world setting.

A. Materials

1) *Data Collection and Preprocess*: This work used real-time data collected in January–February 2024 at the ICAR-CNR IoT Laboratory in Italy. The lab is equipped with indoor/outdoor sensors and actuators, with Raspberry Pi devices acting as edge/cloud nodes for real-time data collection and processing [2]. The dataset includes key variables such as indoor/outdoor temperature, humidity, HVAC status, occupancy, and power consumption. Following our previous [2] work, the collected data were stored in CSV format and loaded into a Pandas DataFrame. The timestamps were converted to the DateTime format, and the data was resampled at 5-minute intervals for consistency. Missing values were filled using forward and backward methods to maintain sequence continuity. Features were classified as numerical (e.g., temperature, humidity, PMV) or categorical (e.g., occupancy, HVAC status, fan speed). Numerical data were scaled using MinMaxScaler, and categorical features were one-hot encoded to prepare the data for DL models.

2) *Data Input Sequences and Split*: This work uses a sliding window approach with 60 time steps of 5 minutes each (5 hours) as input and a 12-step (1 hour) forecast horizon. Each input sequence consists of the following features: indoor temperature, outdoor temperature, HVAC outlet temperature, HVAC power, indoor PMV, outdoor PMV, indoor relative humidity, outdoor relative humidity, occupancy status, and HVAC operational status. The output forecasts future indoor temperature.

A multi-step direct strategy is used, predicting all future steps in one pass. The model is HVAC-aware, using HVAC status as an input and tracking it during forecasting. The dataset was divided into training (70%), validation (15%), and testing (15%) sets to ensure balanced evaluation. HVAC status for the forecast horizon was preserved in all sets, allowing analysis under both HVAC ON and OFF conditions.

Let the input be a multivariate time series as, $X = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_T] \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times d}$, where: T is the sequence length (e.g., 60 time steps), d is the number of input features (e.g., temperature, humidity, HVAC status, occupancy, etc.).

B. AI-Driven Models

iTempDT relies on a TCN and a custom attention mechanism. These models were chosen because of their stable

Fig. 1: Overall Architecture of iTempDT

gradients, parallel processing, and strong ability to learn long-range temporal patterns.

This work uses a TCN block composed of stacked dilated causal 1D convolutions with residual (skip) connections, which help model both short- and long-term temporal dependencies while preserving the sequence order. The dilation rates are set as, $d = \{1, 2, 4\}$, and the kernel size is $k = 2$, allowing the model to capture temporal patterns at multiple resolutions. The TCN transforms the input into a sequence of hidden representations, $H = \text{TCN}(X) \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times h}$, where h is the number of output channels (filters) of the TCN (e.g., $h = 64$).

To enhance the model's ability to focus on important time steps, this work uses an attention block. The attention mechanism computes relevance scores for each time step in the TCN output and combines them into a weighted context vector. Specifically, for each time step $t \in \{1, \dots, T\}$, the attention score is computed as, $e_t = \tanh(W_a h_t + b_a)$, where: $h_t \in \mathbb{R}^h$ is the TCN output at time step t , $W_a \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times h}$ and $b_a \in \mathbb{R}$ are learnable parameters. These scores are then normalized using the softmax function: $\alpha_t = \frac{\exp(e_t)}{\sum_{i=1}^T \exp(e_i)}$, where α_t is the attention weight for time step t , satisfying $\sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t = 1$. The final context vector $c \in \mathbb{R}^h$ is computed as the weighted sum of the TCN outputs as, $c = \sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t h_t$. This context vector represents the most informative temporal features for the forecasting task, especially useful under varying HVAC ON/OFF conditions, where the influence of past time steps can vary significantly.

C. Output Layer

The attention block output is passed through a Batch-Normalization layer to enhance generalization and training stability. A Dropout layer (rate 0.2) is added to reduce overfitting, given the limited training data. The final Dense layer uses linear activation to output 12 values, representing indoor temperature forecasts for the next two hours.

Figure 1 shows the architecture of the proposed iTempDT model. It processes a 60-step multivariate input using a TCN block (64 filters, kernel size 2, dilations [1, 2, 4]) with skip connections. An attention block then generates a context vector using attention weights. A dense layer outputs 12-step forecasts. The model is trained with the Adam optimizer and regularized using EarlyStopping and ReduceLROnPlateau.

D. Training Configuration

The model is implemented in TensorFlow/Keras and trained using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of $1e-4$, which provides adaptive learning. The loss function is Mean Absolute Error (MAE), selected for its robustness to outliers and interpretability in real-world temperature units. To avoid overfitting and accelerate convergence, we used ReduceLROnPlateau, which reduces the learning rate by a factor of 0.5 if validation loss plateaus for 5 epochs. In addition, EarlyStopping was applied with a patience of 7 epochs to stop training when the model performance on the validation set no longer improves. The batch size was set to 32, and training was performed for up to 200 epochs.

E. Evaluations

To evaluate model performance comprehensively, we used three key metrics: Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Coefficient of Determination (R^2), and Ratio of Performance to Deviation (RPD). These metrics capture different aspects of forecasting accuracy and generalization.

1) *Mean Absolute Error (MAE)*: measures the average magnitude of the errors without considering their direction. It is defined as: $\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |y_i - \hat{y}_i|$,

where y_i is the true value, \hat{y}_i is the predicted value, and N is the number of samples.

2) *Coefficient of Determination (R^2)*: quantifies the proportion of variance in the true values explained by the model: $R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$, where \bar{y} is the mean of the actual values.

3) *Ratio of Performance to Deviation (RPD)*: is a reliability indicator that relates the model's prediction error to the natural variability in the data. It is defined as: $\text{RPD} = \frac{\sigma_y}{\text{RMSE}}$, where σ_y is the standard deviation of the true values and RMSE is the root mean squared error of the predictions. A higher RPD indicates better model robustness; values above 2.0 are generally considered good for predictive applications.

In addition, we conducted scenario-specific evaluations by splitting the test set based on HVAC activity. Sequences where it was ON (status = 1) and OFF (status = 0) were evaluated separately. This allowed us to assess the model's generalization capability across different system operation modes and better understand its performance under varying thermal dynamics.

Indoor Temperature Forecasting Dashboard (iTempDT)

Fig. 2: iTempDT Dashboard in Digital Shadow mode; actuation-ready for future Raspberry Pi-based Digital Twin control.

F. Deployment and Efficiency Evaluation: Toward Green AI

To enable the practical deployment of the iTempDT approach in edge or low-power environments, this work adopted model quantization as a key step toward Green AI. Quantization reduces the numerical precision of the model weights and activations, leading to significant improvements in efficiency without substantial loss in prediction performance. This work applies Float16 quantization to compress the trained model, reducing model size and improving inference efficiency.

This approach was selected for its simplicity, compatibility, and ability to maintain prediction accuracy while significantly reducing model size and computational load. Float16 quantization enabled efficient deployment of the DT model in resource-constrained environments, aligning with the principles of Green AI by promoting energy-efficient ML/DL.

IV. RESULT ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

An iTempDT prototype was developed at the ICAR-CNR IoT Lab using an Intel Core i7-7567U with 16 GB RAM. It was implemented in Python with libraries including Pandas, NumPy, Matplotlib, Scikit-learn, TensorFlow, and Keras. An interactive dashboard, built with ipywidgets, was also

developed to support real-time forecasting, HVAC control simulation, and visualization, enabling full DT functionality. The following section presents the results of the iTempDT approach.

A. The Dashboard

iTempDT includes a dashboard that links real-time sensor data with predictive models for HVAC simulation. The implemented dashboard (reported in Figure 2) acts as a virtual version of the indoor space, updated with live sensor data. It uses the introduced model to forecast the indoor temperature based on the status of the HVAC (ON/OFF), occupancy, humidity, and outdoor conditions. At present, it operates in Digital Shadow mode, supporting real-time monitoring and predictive “what-if” analysis without directly controlling the physical HVAC system. In future deployments, it will be connected to the HVAC system via a Raspberry Pi edge device, enabling closed-loop actuation and transforming iTempDT into a fully functional DT. This helps safely explore energy-saving strategies in SBs.

The dashboard provides a set of intuitive widgets to support exploratory analysis. There is a *Sample Selector*, a slider that

Fig. 3: Training and Validation Loss on ICAR CNR Data

Fig. 4: Actual vs Forecasted indoor temperature from the test dataset

allows you to browse different time windows from the test set. Each sample shows a specific time interval. Moreover, an *HVAC Mode* selector lets users change the HVAC control setting for forecasting. A user can choose to *Use Original* to keep the actual HVAC status from the dataset/real-time. Otherwise, *Force ON / Force OFF* can be selected to simulate the HVAC staying ON or OFF throughout the forecast, ignoring the original status.

Regarding the *Forecast Buttons*, two forecast views are available: (i) *Model Forecast with Input*: Shows past input data, forecast, and actual values for full context; (ii) *Only Model Forecast*: Displays only actual vs. forecast future values to focus on accuracy.

The *Real Time* button is designed to trigger forecasts using live data from SB sensors. This enables real-time updates and feedback within the DT system, supporting continuous monitoring and control.

By summarizing, the dashboard generates and visualizes time-series plots showing:

- Historical indoor temperatures (when selected),
- Actual vs. predicted future indoor temperatures,
- A vertical line marking the transition from input to forecast (forecast start time).

The plot updates in real time based on user input, showing the model’s response to HVAC changes.

B. Training and Validation Loss

Figure 3 shows the training and validation loss curves over 80 epochs using the ICAR-CNR dataset, with loss measured

TABLE I: Performance comparison of models under HVAC ON and OFF conditions using MAE, R^2 , and RPD metrics

Models	HVAC Status	MAE	R^2	RPD
ANN	HVAC_ON	0.028934	0.84802	4.395415
	HVAC_OFF	0.037531	0.815109	2.957813
RNN	HVAC_ON	0.026368	0.940058	5.018441
	HVAC_OFF	0.04656	0.890366	3.029884
CNN	HVAC_ON	0.033574	0.946144	4.311764
	HVAC_OFF	0.03987	0.887608	2.984933
LSTM	HVAC_ON	0.022012	0.95242	4.175863
	HVAC_OFF	0.02952	0.891508	3.046211
iTempDT	HVAC_ON	0.021945	0.963542	5.241733
	HVAC_OFF	0.028641	0.924126	3.63405

as scaled MAE. Although training was set for 100 epochs, early stopping halted it at epoch 83 to prevent overfitting. Both curves drop quickly in the early stages and then converge smoothly. The close match between training and validation losses reflects the strong generalization ability of the iTempDT model for indoor temperature forecasting.

C. Actual vs Forecasted Indoor Temperature

Figure 4 shows a comparison between actual and forecasted indoor temperatures in the first 200 time steps of the test set. The forecast closely follows the real temperature trends, capturing both sudden changes and gradual shifts. The small gap between the two lines indicates high accuracy and strong generalization. These results confirm the effectiveness of the iTempDT approach in modeling indoor temperature dynamics under varying conditions.

D. Comparative Analysis with State-of-the-Art Models

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed iTempDT, this work compares it with several baseline and state-of-the-art DL models: Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM). For a fair comparison, all models were designed with comparable depth and number of layers, ensuring that differences in performance reflect architectural strengths rather than capacity or parameter count.

Table I compares model performance under HVAC ON and OFF conditions using MAE, R^2 , and RPD metrics.

The iTempDT significantly outperforms baseline architectures such as ANN, RNN, CNN, and LSTM under both HVAC ON and HVAC OFF conditions. iTempDT achieves the lowest MAE (0.021945) and highest R^2 (0.9635) when HVAC is ON, and maintains robust performance with MAE = 0.0286 and R^2 = 0.9241 in HVAC OFF scenarios. Its RPD values above 3.6 in both cases indicate high reliability and predictive strength. These results reflect the architectural advantages of iTempDT.

Among the baseline models, LSTM performs competitively, particularly in HVAC ON conditions, with an MAE of 0.022012 and R^2 of 0.9524. However, its performance degrades more in HVAC OFF scenarios compared to iTempDT. RNN also shows strong results when HVAC is ON but suffers significant performance loss when HVAC is OFF, indicating less generalization ability in passive thermal dynamics.

ANN and CNN models perform comparatively worse, especially under HVAC OFF conditions, where lower R^2 and

TABLE II: Performance on Quantized iTempDT on various metrics

Model	HVAC Status	MAE	R ²	RPD
<i>iTempDT</i>	HVAC_ON	0.0206	0.96	5.0066
<i>Quantized</i>	HVAC_OFF	0.0262	0.917	3.4751

RPD values suggest poorer adaptability to indoor temperature variations without active system intervention.

In summary, iTempDT uses TCN to learn short- and long-term patterns quickly and reliably. The attention block helps focus on key past moments, especially when HVAC is OFF. Including HVAC status as input lets the model handle both OFF and ON conditions. These features make it accurate, flexible, and ideal for SBs' DTs.

E. Model Quantization and Edge Deployment Performance: Toward Green AI

To evaluate deployment on low-power devices, Float16 post-training quantization was applied to the iTempDT model using TensorFlow Lite. The goal was to reduce model size and inference time while maintaining good forecast accuracy, supporting Green AI principles. The evaluation included:

- Prediction Accuracy Metrics: MAE, R², and RPD.
- Model Size (MB): Indicates storage and memory needs.
- Inference Time (ms): Time taken per prediction.
- FLOPs: It refers to the number of mathematical operations to be done during inference.

1) *Metrics of Quantized iTempDT*: Table II shows quantized iTempDT results evaluated under HVAC ON and HVAC OFF conditions, respectively.

The quantized model achieved a MAE of 0.0262, R² of 0.917, and RPD of 3.4751 under HVAC OFF conditions. While there is a slight drop in performance compared to the original iTempDT (which achieved MAE = 0.0206 and R² = 0.96 under HVAC ON), the results still indicate high predictive quality and robustness.

This trade-off is justified by the significant reduction in model size and computational demand, enabling the model to be deployed on edge devices such as Raspberry Pi or low-power IoT controllers in SBs. The quantized version maintains strong forecasting capability while being optimized for real-time execution and energy-efficient operation, making it ideal for embedded DT applications.

2) *iTempDT Analysis on Model Size, Inference Time, and Flops*: To extend this work, an analysis of Model Size, Inference Time, and Floating Point Operations (FLOPs) was conducted for both the original iTempDT model and its quantized version. FLOPs represent the total number of arithmetic operations required by the model during inference, regardless of runtime hardware performance. This evaluation highlights the efficiency gains achieved through quantization, demonstrating reduced storage requirements, faster predictions, and lower computational cost, key factors for real-time deployment on edge devices in SB environments.

Table III summarizes the model size, inference time, and FLOPs for both versions. Quantization reduced the model size

from 0.60 MB to 0.11 MB, an 81.7% reduction, which is crucial for deploying the model on low-memory edge devices such as Raspberry Pi or microcontrollers. The inference time improved as well: the average inference latency dropped from 0.0535s to 0.0339s (a 36.6% speed-up) when tested on 100 samples over 5 runs. This performance boost was achieved without modifying the model structure. The FLOPs remained the same (5,259,190) in both models. This is because quantization reduces precision, not the number of operations. The architecture and layer sizes remain unchanged. As a result, the computational pathway is identical, but each operation is executed more efficiently with float16 arithmetic.

These results show that quantization greatly reduces model size and inference time while maintaining accuracy. This makes iTempDT suitable for real-world SBs with limited resources, supporting Green AI and edge-based DT deployment.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This work presented the design and the development of iTempDT, a DT approach for forecasting indoor temperature in HVAC-enabled smart buildings (SBs). The approach combines a TCN-Attention-based deep learning model with an easy-to-use interactive dashboard, allowing users to simulate and visualize temperature changes under different HVAC settings. The model performs accurately in forecasting future temperature trends and is able to clearly distinguish between HVAC ON and OFF states. One of the key strengths of this system is its ability to support smarter HVAC control decisions, helping to reduce energy use while maintaining indoor comfort. The quantized version of the model further enables deployment on low-power edge devices, supporting the goals of Green AI by reducing computational cost and improving energy efficiency. In the future, the system will be extended with real-time feedback for automatic HVAC control, turning predictions into closed-loop actions. This will run on a Raspberry Pi at the Edge for fast decisions, moving iTempDT from a Digital Shadow to a full Digital Twin. The model can also be scaled to multiple rooms and enriched with inputs like window/door status, weather forecasts, or user preferences to improve accuracy and usability. Overall, this work advances smart and sustainable buildings by combining Digital Twins and AI to save energy while maintaining occupant comfort.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Savaglio, V. Barbuto, F. M. Awan, R. Minerva, N. Crespi, and G. Fortino, "Opportunistic digital twin: an edge intelligence enabler for smart city," *ACM Transactions on Sensor Networks*, 2023.
- [2] M. B. Islam, A. Guerrieri, R. Gravina, and G. Fortino, "A deep learning based digital twin for indoor temperature prediction in smart buildings," in *2024 IEEE Conference on Pervasive and Intelligent Computing (PICom)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 83–89.
- [3] S. Taheri, P. Hosseini, and A. Razban, "Model predictive control of heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (hvac) systems: A state-of-the-art review," *Journal of Building Engineering*, vol. 60, p. 105067, 2022.
- [4] K. Jeong, C. Koo, and T. Hong, "An estimation model for determining the annual energy cost budget in educational facilities using sarima (seasonal autoregressive integrated moving average) and ann (artificial neural network)," *Energy*, vol. 71, pp. 71–79, 2014.

TABLE III: Model Size, Inference Time, and Flops between iTempDT and its Quantized Version

Model	Model Size (MB)	Inference Time (s)		Inference Time (s)		FLOPs
		Mean	Std	Min	Max	
<i>iTempDT</i>	0.6	0.0535	0.0082	0.0459	0.0688	5259190
<i>Quantized iTempDT</i>	0.11	0.0339	0.0021	0.0319	0.0379	5259190

- [5] F. Zhang, C. Deb, S. E. Lee, J. Yang, and K. W. Shah, "Time series forecasting for building energy consumption using weighted support vector regression with differential evolution optimization technique," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 126, pp. 94–103, 2016.
- [6] M. W. Ahmad, M. Mourshed, and Y. Rezgui, "Trees vs neurons: Comparison between random forest and ann for high-resolution prediction of building energy consumption," *Energy and buildings*, vol. 147, pp. 77–89, 2017.
- [7] Y. Huang, H. Miles, and P. Zhang, "A sequential modelling approach for indoor temperature prediction and heating control in smart buildings," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2009.09847*, 2020.
- [8] S. Alawadi, D. Mera, M. Fernández-Delgado, F. Alkhabbas, C. M. Olsson, and P. Davidsson, "A comparison of machine learning algorithms for forecasting indoor temperature in smart buildings," *Energy Systems*, pp. 1–17, 2020.
- [9] E. K. Ampomah, Z. Qin, and G. Nyame, "Evaluation of tree-based ensemble machine learning models in predicting stock price direction of movement," *Information*, vol. 11, no. 6, p. 332, 2020.
- [10] M. Manivannan, B. Najafi, and F. Rinaldi, "Machine learning-based short-term prediction of air-conditioning load through smart meter analytics," *Energies*, vol. 10, no. 11, p. 1905, 2017.
- [11] A. Kusiak, G. Xu, and Z. Zhang, "Minimization of energy consumption in hvac systems with data-driven models and an interior-point method," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 85, pp. 146–153, 2014.
- [12] A. E. Ben-Nakhi and M. A. Mahmoud, "Energy conservation in buildings through efficient a/c control using neural networks," *Applied Energy*, vol. 73, no. 1, pp. 5–23, 2002.
- [13] X. Wei, A. Kusiak, M. Li, F. Tang, and Y. Zeng, "Multi-objective optimization of the hvac (heating, ventilation, and air conditioning) system performance," *Energy*, vol. 83, pp. 294–306, 2015.
- [14] P. A. Mirzaei, F. Haghghat, A. A. Nakhaie, A. Yagouti, M. Giguère, R. Keusseyan, and A. Coman, "Indoor thermal condition in urban heat island—development of a predictive tool," *Building and Environment*, vol. 57, pp. 7–17, 2012.
- [15] T. Lu and M. Viljanen, "Prediction of indoor temperature and relative humidity using neural network models: model comparison," *Neural Computing and Applications*, vol. 18, pp. 345–357, 2009.
- [16] Z. Afroz, T. Urme, G. Shafiullah, and G. Higgins, "Real-time prediction model for indoor temperature in a commercial building," *Applied energy*, vol. 231, pp. 29–53, 2018.
- [17] L. Mba, P. Meukam, and A. Kemajou, "Application of artificial neural network for predicting hourly indoor air temperature and relative humidity in modern building in humid region," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 121, pp. 32–42, 2016.
- [18] W. Yu, B. Nakisa, E. Ali, S. W. Loke, S. Stevanovic, and Y. Guo, "Sensor-based indoor air temperature prediction using deep ensemble machine learning: An australian urban environment case study," *Urban Climate*, vol. 51, p. 101599, 2023.
- [19] C. Xu, H. Chen, J. Wang, Y. Guo, and Y. Yuan, "Improving prediction performance for indoor temperature in public buildings based on a novel deep learning method," *Building and Environment*, vol. 148, pp. 128–135, 2019.
- [20] J. Song, G. Xue, Y. Ma, H. Li, Y. Pan, and Z. Hao, "An indoor temperature prediction framework based on hierarchical attention gated recurrent unit model for energy efficient buildings," *Ieee Access*, vol. 7, pp. 157 268–157 283, 2019.
- [21] Z. Fang, N. Crimier, L. Scanu, A. Midelet, A. Alyafi, and B. Delinchant, "Multi-zone indoor temperature prediction with lstm-based sequence to sequence model," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 245, p. 111053, 2021.
- [22] A. Dhakal and K. Ramakrishnan, "Machine learning at the network edge for automated home intrusion monitoring," in *2017 IEEE 25th International Conference on Network Protocols (ICNP)*. IEEE, 2017, pp. 1–6.
- [23] Z. Ni, Y. Liu, M. Karlsson, and S. Gong, "Enabling preventive conservation of historic buildings through cloud-based digital twins: A case study in the city theatre, norrköping," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 90924–90 939, 2022.
- [24] Z. Ni, P. Eriksson, Y. Liu, M. Karlsson, and S. Gong, "Improving energy efficiency while preserving historic buildings with digital twins and artificial intelligence," in *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, vol. 863, no. 1. IOP Publishing, 2021, p. 012041.
- [25] J. Zhang, H. H. Kwok, H. Luo, J. C. Tong, and J. C. Cheng, "Automatic relative humidity optimization in underground heritage sites through ventilation system based on digital twins," *Building and Environment*, vol. 216, p. 108999, 2022.
- [26] Y. Wang, H. Wu, J. Dong, Y. Liu, M. Long, and J. Wang, "Deep time series models: A comprehensive survey and benchmark," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2407.13278*, 2024.
- [27] L. Wei, Z. Ma, C. Yang, and Q. Yao, "Advances in the neural network quantization: A comprehensive review," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 14, no. 17, p. 7445, 2024.
- [28] V. Bolón-Canedo, L. Morán-Fernández, B. Cancela, and A. Alonso-Betanzos, "A review of green artificial intelligence: Towards a more sustainable future," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 599, p. 128096, 2024.
- [29] M. B. Islam, A. Guerrieri, R. Gravina, and G. Fortino, "A meta-survey on intelligent energy-efficient buildings," *Big Data and Cognitive Computing*, vol. 8, no. 8, p. 83, 2024.
- [30] M. B. Islam, A. Guerrieri, R. Gravina, L. Rizzo, G. Scopelliti, V. D'Agostino, and G. Fortino, "A review on machine learning for thermal comfort and energy efficiency in smart buildings," in *Proceedings of the 2023 INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON EMBEDDED WIRELESS SYSTEMS AND NETWORKS*, 2023, pp. 243–248.
- [31] H. Hosamo, M. H. Hosamo, H. K. Nielsen, P. R. Svennevig, and K. Svidt, "Digital twin of hvac system (hvacdt) for multiobjective optimization of energy consumption and thermal comfort based on bim framework with ann-moga," *Advances in building energy research*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 125–171, 2023.
- [32] Q. Lu, X. Xie, A. K. Parlikad, and J. M. Schooling, "Digital twin-enabled anomaly detection for built asset monitoring in operation and maintenance," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 118, p. 103277, 2020.
- [33] S. Liu, P. Si, M. Xu, Y. He, and Y. Zhang, "Edge big data-enabled low-cost indoor localization based on bayesian analysis of rss," in *2017 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC)*. IEEE, 2017, pp. 1–6.
- [34] S. K. Singh, M. Kumar, S. Tanwar, and J. H. Park, "Gru-based digital twin framework for data allocation and storage in iot-enabled smart home networks," *Future Generation Computer Systems*, vol. 153, pp. 391–402, 2024.